

Association for Conscious and Freedom
Romanian Academy / National Institute of Economic Research /
Centre for Mountain Economy
The Academy of Romanian Scientists / Military Sciences Section
The Academy of National Security Sciences
The Academy of Agricultural and Forestry Sciences /
Institute of Research and Development for Montanology
The Institute for Peace Studies in Eastern Christianity

1st International Workshop

SCIENTIFIC RESEARCH AND ACADEMIC ETHICS

Romanian Academy / National Institute of Economic Research /
Centre for Mountain Economy – Kiritescu Hall

BUCHAREST
October 3rd, 2019

The workshop is part of the International Conference
Human Dignity and Religious Freedom, October 1st – 3rd
Palace of the Parliament & Romanian Academy

Scientific Committee

Erhard Busek. *Austrian Vice-Chancellor (former) & Institute for Danube Region and Central Europe – Austria*

Radu Rey. *Romanian Academy / National Institute of Economic Research / Centre for Mountain Economy*

Teodor Frunzeti. *The Academy of Romanian Scientists / Military Sciences Section – Romania*

Viorel Buta. *The Academy of National Security Sciences – Romania*

Brindusa Covaci. *Romanian Academy National Institute of Economic Research, Adventus University – Romania & Centre for Risk Studies in Economic and Social Sciences – Austria*

Nelu Burcea. *Public Affairs and Religious Liberty Department Associate Director at the General Conference of the Seventh-day Adventists & The representative of the Seventh Day Adventist Church and International Religious Liberty Association to the United Nations in New York and Geneva – United States of America*

Marian Simion. *Harvard Divinity School & The Institute for Peace Studies in Eastern Christianity – United States of America*

Daive Barbieri. *Oxford University (Fellow) – United Kingdom & Link Campus University Intelligence – Italy*

Gabriel Xiao-Guang Yue. *Rattanakosin International College of Creative Entrepreneurship / Rajamangala University of Technology Rattanakosin – Thailand & Siksha 'O' Anusandhan University – India*

Andrian Vladimirov Aleksandrov. *Sofia University “St. Kliment Ohridski” – Bulgaria*

Mariana Rusu. *The Academy of Agricultural and Forestry Sciences / Institute of Research and Development for Montanology – Romania*

Tamara Peicu. *University of Vienna – Austria*

David Harms. *Friedensau Adventist University (Fellow) – Germany & Andrews University – United States of America*

Artur Boldt. *Bogenhofen Seminary (Fellow) – Austria & Andrews University – United States of America*

Organizing Committee

Ioan-Gheorghe Rotaru. *‘Timotheus’ Brethren Theological Institute – Romania*

Dragos Musat. *Association for Conscious and Freedom – Romania*

Paul Brusanski. *“Lucian Blaga” University – Romania*

Zorica Triff. *Technical University of Cluj-Napoca / North University Center from Baia Mare – Romania*

Dumitru Vanca. "1 Decembrie 1918" University – Romania

Mihai Covaci. Hyperion University – Romania & Centre for Risk Studies in Economic and Social Sciences – Austria

Viorica Burcea. Research Association for Interdisciplinary Studies – United States of America

Liana Rozalia Rotaru. The County Center of Resources and Educational Assistance – Romania

Otilia Manta. Romanian Academy / "Victor Slavescu" Center for Financial and Monetary Research, "Athenaeum" University of Bucharest – Romania & School of International University Studies / Instituto di Ricerca di Dr. Arioli S.a.s. – Italy

Consuela Wagner. Institut für Bildung und Persönlichkeitsförderung – Germany

Participants Registration: Romanian Academy / National Institute of Economic Research / Centre for Mountain Economy – Kiritescu Hall (09.00 – 10.00)

Welcome Speeches (10.00 – 10.10)

Brindusa Covaci. Romanian Academy / National Institute of Economic Research & Centre for Risk Studies in Economic and Social Sciences – Austria

Ioan-Gheorghe Rotaru. 'Timotheus' Brethren Theological Institute – Romania

Keynote Speeches (10.10 – 11.10)

Teodor Frunzeti. The Academy of Romanian Scientists / Military Sciences Section – Romania

Paper: *The Academic Ethics and the Compliance with Historical Truth*

Marian Simion. Harvard Divinity School – United States of America

Paper: *Culture and Academic Ethics in Scientific Research*

Mihai Himcinschi. "1 Decembrie 1918" University – Romania

Paper: *Ethics and Integrity in Current Academic Research*

Emil Jurcan. "1 Decembrie 1918" University – Romania

Paper: *Academic Ethics, between Vocation and Educational Mission*

Break (11.10 – 11.30)

Section I – Society, Scientific Research and Academic Ethics (11.30 – 12.30)

*Chair: **Brindusa Covaci.** Romanian Academy / National Institute of Economic Research & Centre for Risk Studies in Economic and Social Sciences – Austria*

*Discussants: **Radu Rey.** Romanian Academy / National Institute of Economic Research / Centre for Mountain Economy*

***Viorel Buta.** The Academy of National Security Sciences – Romania*

Carpathians of Romania in the 21 st Century, between Decline and Hope. Recovery, through the Preservation of Traditional Values, the Quality of "Mountain Products", Specific Organization and Education and Through Creation of a "Mountain Culture" at Institutional Level and in Society	Radu Rey. Romanian Academy / National Institute of Economic Research / Centre for Mountain Economy
Realities and Perspectives of the Romanian Research in the Defense Science in the New European Context	Viorel Buta & Mihail Anton. The Academy of National Security Sciences – Romania
Social Prerequisites for Successful Ethical Education	Consuela Wagner. Institut für Bildung und Persönlichkeitsförderung – Germany
Academic Ethics in the Economic Sciences. Case Study for Romanian Scientific Research	Brindusa Covaci. Romanian Academy / National Institute of Economic Research & Centre for Risk Studies in Economic and Social Sciences – Austria
Phd in Romania Today: Challenges and Perspectives	Gheorghe Negustor. "Babes-Bolyai" University – Romania
Scientific and Ethical Methods and Techniques Addressed in Advising Pupils and Students	Liana Rozalia Rotaru. The County Center of Resources and Educational Assistance – Romania
Academics Ethics in Bulgaria: Cultural Challenges and State Policy	Andrian Vladimirov Aleksandrov. Sofia University "St. Kliment Ohridski" – Bulgaria

The Impact of Ethical Values on Academic Values and Results	Otilia Manta. <i>Romanian Academy / "Victor Slavescu" Center for Financial and Monetary Research, "Athenaeum" University of Bucharest – Romania & School of International University Studies / Istituto di Ricerca di Dr. Arioli S.a.s. – Italy</i>
Effects of the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) on the Scientific Research in Romania	Nicoleta Mihaila. <i>Romanian Academy / "Victor Slavescu" Center for Financial and Monetary Research – Romania</i>
Scientific Observation. Qualitative Field Research and Ethical Principles of Scientific Research	Gheorghe Radu. <i>Athenaeum University – Romania</i>
Academic Ethics in the Context of Alternative University Education (Public and Private) - Provocations and Reconsiderations	Dumitru Nica. <i>The National Defense University Carol I – Romania</i>
Scientific Research with Mountain Specific in Support of Consolidation of Peasant Farming	Mariana Rusu. <i>The Academy of Agricultural and Forestry Sciences / Institute of Research and Development for Montanology – Romania</i>
Academic Activism and Ethical Neutrality in Scientific Research	Tamara Abigail Peicu. <i>University of Vienna – Austria</i>
Academic Ethics in the Education Science. Case Study for Romanian Scientific Research	Mihai Covaci. <i>Hyperion University – Romania & Centre for Risk Studies in Economic and Social Sciences – Austria</i>
Cultivating Ethical Values through the Study of Social Sciences	Marius Barcuteanu. <i>Tehnicul Anghel Saligny College – Romania</i>
Questions and answers	

Section II – Humanity, Scientific Research and Academic Ethics (12.30 – 13.30)

Chair: Ioan-Gheorghe Rotaru. "Timotheus' Brethren Theological Institute – Romania

Discussants: Serban Turcus. "Babes-Bolyai" University – Romania

Stelian Manolache. "Ovidius" University – Romania

Ethical Conditioning over the Last Decade History between Challenges of Nationalism and those of Globalization	Serban Turcus. <i>"Babes-Bolyai" University – Romania & Veronica Turcus.</i> <i>Romanian Academy Cluj-Napoca / "George Baritiu" History Institute – Romania</i>
Research Methodology in Church History	Paul Brusanowski. <i>"Lucian Blaga" University – Romania</i>
Ethical and Moral in Setting Thresholds Regarding the Level of Similarities in Undergraduate and Graduate Theses	Dumitru Vanca. <i>"1 Decembrie 1918" University – Romania</i>
Science and Communication in Academic Ethics	Denise E. Burrill. <i>Fitchburg State University – United States of America</i>
The Relationship between Academic Ethics and the Author's Morality	Stelian Manolache. <i>"Ovidius" University – Romania</i>
Divine Principles of the Decalogue and Plagiarism	Ieremia Rusu. <i>"Timotheus' Brethren Theological Institute – Romania</i>
The Freedom of Access to Knowledge as a Moral Valu	Osman Murat Deniz. <i>Çanakkale Onsekiz Mart Üniversitesi – Turkey</i>
The Rules and Limits of Ethics of Teaching Interfaith to Students of Your Confession	Tudor-Cosmin Ciocan. <i>University „Ovidius” – Romania</i>
Modalities of Preventive and Therapeutic Intervention in Child Abuse through the Ethical Aspects	Zorica Aurica Triff. <i>Technical University of Cluj-Napoca / North University Center from Baia Mare – Romania</i>
Ethical and Praxiological Scientific Approaches in the Training and Professional Development of	Delia Mariana Ardelean. <i>„Vasile Goldis" University – Romania</i>

Teachers	
Perspectives in Scientific Research and Ethical Aspects of the Use of Electronic Records of Medical Data	Dorin-Gheorghe Triff. <i>Technical University of Cluj-Napoca / North University Center from Baia Mare – Romania</i>
Current Challenges in Research Ethics within the University Environment	Iulian Militaru. <i>Romanian-American University – Romania</i>
Investigative and Proactive Scientific Research	Antoneta Bolchis. <i>Maramures School Inspectorate – Romania</i>
Guiding Principles in the Ethical Code of Science	Arthur Wagner. <i>Independent Scholar – Germany</i>
Questions and answers	

Conclusions and Closing Speeches (13.30 – 14.00)

Tamara Abigail Peicu. *University of Vienna – Austria*

Gheorghe Radu. *Athenaeum University – Romania*

Otilia Manta. *Romanian Academy / "Victor Slavescu" Center for Financial and Monetary Research, "Athenaeum" University of Bucharest – Romania & School of International University Studies / Istituto di Ricerca di Dr. Arioli S.a.s. – Italy*

Dragos Musat. *Association for Conscious and Freedom – Romania*